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The idea of this document is to explore the meaning and possibilities of data integration and to propose some path which can be taken by the SAGA group to go further.

To introduce the subject, let us look at the results of a keyword searching on the web of science database. The Table 1 details these results. We can conclude that compared to the whole literature on data integration, its application in geoarchaeology is not so widespread or at least, it is not called data integration. The fact of using another word like fusion does not increase the numbers so much. This means that some definition of what we call data integration is needed.

This document will try to gather the ideas of some members of the WG3 on the subject, as we understand it. This is a not so accurate summary of what have been discussed, what we have read and we hope it will make things clearer. Writing this document allows us to see how the subject could be enhanced by tasks from other members of the group. When we feel it necessary, we have mentioned them and we encourage the reader to go and have look to the results of these task for deeper reading on the subject.

Keyword combination	Findings last 5 years	Finding all years
Data+integration (articles/reviews)		141590 (96187/6429)
Data+fusion (articles/reviews)		87668 (61251/3012)
Data+integration+geosciences	81	208
Data+fusion+geosciences		60
Data+integration+archaeology	118	255
Data+fusion+archaeology		54
Data+integration+archaeology+geosciences	1	3
Data+fusion+archaeology+geosciences		1

Table 1: Findings on the Web of Science database using the keywords mentioned

Firstly, we are going to define data. Based on the online Etymology Dictionary (<https://www.etymonline.com/word/data>) the first English use of the word “data” goes back to 1640s and in 1946 was first used to convey the meaning of "transmissible and storable computer information". Data are reliable things or characteristics collected through observation that can be used to build some line of thoughts or theories. The first step is the data collection/measurement, followed by the visualization using graphs or images. The subsequent analysis using suitable tools can transform the data to information and knowledge suitable for drawing conclusions, proposing theories, formulating strategies, making decisions etc.

There are different types and kinds of data including but not limited to: scientific, geographical, cultural, natural, meteorological, statistical, financial etc. A common view implies a chain of serial actions. Especially, in terms of archaeological prospection the variety of data exhibits a certain diversity spanning for example from an archaeological artifact, to a historical map or a raw voltage measurement integrated in a spatial and temporal framework.

Some interesting thoughts about noise in geophysical prospecting could be found in Dabas et al. (in preparation:M Dabas, announced it on this task forum). There is also an interesting paper in

Geophysics by Scales and Snieder (1998) “What is noise?” According to the paper noise can be defined as the part of data we choose not to explain, which assumes the existence of a model that explains the “clean” data. If this is not the case it automatically means that “noise” is including significant information.

This first step setup, how data integration is defined? Referring to some articles (Kvamme et al. 2019, Cuenca Garcia 2018, Golshan et al 2017, Kalayci 2015, Halevy et al 2006, Lenzerini 2002) data integration is the combination of data residing at different sources in order to provide a unified interface to view, manage, process and interpret them. Data integration comprises a theoretical and technological challenge in an effort to query among multiple autonomous and heterogeneous data sources resulting in a unified processing and interpretative directive. In other words, it means that the data types should be somehow linked to manage them in a holistic way, at the same time taking into account:

- a) the complexity of integration as in specific contexts it is not entirely clear what data integration means or how the different data sets can complement each other,
- b) the degree of uncertainty and inconsistency of the multiple data sets proposing automatic or semi-automatic approaches to deal with this aspect,
- c) the time, space and computational constraints of such an effort.

. So the first question you should ask yourself is:

1- What kind of link can I use to integrate my data?

Here we have listed what links came up during the discussion and I have added some literature when it is useful. These ways to make links could appear obvious, but there were the ones on which we were agreeing. Like all the list in this document, it is open, and one research path could be to look for other ways to link the data.

Object of study

If the link you have is your object (a site, a soil sample), one first classical way to include “integrated” in the title of the study is to employ various methods on the same objects. You are adding points of view from several scientific disciplines, hoping something will come out. This is to emphasize that the complexity of the integration will increase with the degree of heterogeneity of the data (for example, it would be easier to integrate various geophysical datasets together than to integrate geophysical or geochemical data to an archaeological model). Each method / data set will bring a piece of the whole and if you are lucky, the understanding of your object will be better. After that, you will have a model of your object which can be used for doing somehow data integration on other similar objects.

Spatial coordinates

As long as we are dealing with data that can be located with spatial coordinates, we have a link. Overlapping maps, combining aerial photographs and satellite images, relating coring with geophysical prospecting results could be considered as a first level of integration. Fortunately, when you are dealing with spatially referenced datasets, unified interfaces exist in the shape of GIS software. Concerning geophysical prospecting, the chapter by Kvamme et al. (2018) is very complete.

Prior model

This category is closely linked to the first one. The main difference is that the relationships are established by any means (statistics, physics, pedotransfer function, experimental equations linking different physical quantities, excavation data, machine learning ...). Thus you can use this *a priori* link to integrate your datasets and see if the interpreted results are enhanced by their integration. It

is the path that you are following if you are doing joint inversion in geophysics. It is also the path which brings you to define your relationship in a semantic model. This last approach is useful especially when you have very heterogeneous data types.

The first and the third way are closely related, but they differ from the way you are looking at it. The first one is more attributed to the question, “if I am looking at something by various ways, do I have a better knowledge of it?” On the opposite, the third one is more related to a question of the kind “Is my model suitable for explaining the data?”

Nonetheless, each cases mentioned are mainly addressed by mathematical methods. These last are used and developed to do the jobs of creating or exhibiting links. Hereafter is an unexhaustive list of these methods:

- based on statistics (e.g. on pedological data by Ivana S. and Marija S. in the WG3 task 2.4)
- based on compositional analysis (e.g. on geochemical data by Jan H. and STSM by Martin J.)
- based on geostatistical model (e.g. in Goovaert 2001)
- based on conceptual model (e.g. in Meghini and Doerr 2018 and Martjin V. L. task 2.2)
- based on physical law (e.g. forward and inverse modeling in geophysics like in Rucker et al. 2017 and STSM by Kleanthis S.)
- based on empirical or semi empirical models (e.g. pedotransfer function, Mc Bratney et al. 2002)

It has to be noticed that machine learning is somehow a way to do all the above listed techniques but with a highly automated level allowing to address a huge amount of data. (e.g. Pedegrosa et al. 2011 and STSM by Meldá K.). The Scikit-learn site is very well made on many of these aspects (<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/tutorial/basic/tutorial.html#machine-learning-the-problem-setting>).

In the recent literature, you have examples of how it is used to fill or approximate the links (e.g. for pedotransfer function in Benke et al. 2020).

At this point, here the main issue to address is how can I use these link? (And, maybe how people did uses them).

2- How can I integrate my data?

Descriptive step

First, you can overlap or concatenate your data. It means that you have a coordinate system which is common. Either if they are pictures or georeferenced dataset, you can view in some mapping software (e.g. in the following part). Some examples can be found in Conyers et al 2018 or in Krivanek 2017.

Nonetheless, it is data integration in a representative point of view (aiming to have different view of a same object, each one independent from the others). Maybe here we have some kind of zero ground level of integration. Very few hypotheses are supporting there are links between your data.

Modeling

Do I have link (e.g.; structural, physical, statistical etc.) between my datasets which is somewhat different from the spatial relationship. Here you can use one or several method listed above. You try to understand the relationship between your datasets or to enlighten the ones you know a priori (and maybe to exhibit discrepancies of your case with some other). In any case you are starting to think to establish a model. It could be any kind of model and the order of the list given above is based on how your *a priori* hypotheses are numerous. A first effort to propose different integration methods in synthetic geophysical data is presented by Manataki et al (2015).

To develop this idea, if you do statistical and compositional modeling you need a vague idea on how your overall data distribution is, knowing at the same time the limitation, the approach considered is robust and not very constraining. Adding some constraints, you come to geostatistical

or conceptual model. The first kind of approach is based on the idea that subsurface feature with spatial consistency exist and thus what you are measuring is not completely random. The second kind relies on the fact that you are searching features which are not completely abstract and you can then define relationship between your datasets based on the kind of feature you have. The third kind relies for itself on physical or empirical law which constrains your relationship. Here you have strong a priori information and hope your data have an enough quality to reach your aims. Here we can call it the modeling step. There are some rooms here to go further in the integration like joint inverse modeling in geophysics. Using spatially denser datasets to estimate sparser datasets is regularly done when pedology and geophysics interact (e.g. Pasquier et al. 2016, Wadoux et al. 2019). Here you are dealing basically with data of the same kind (numerical values in table with common labelling or possibility to do so). Maybe we could go further and find ways to link geochemical and geophysical data in some model (empirical or theoretical). An example of the spirit of that is the Archie law which link geophysics and rock physics. The ultimate steps would be archaeological site modelling for what it could means.

Interpretation

The third step is the one where you try to put together things of various nature. Artifacts, stratigraphical units, pictures, any data representation. If you are lucky, everything could be represented as a picture and you are very close to the second step. If not, you are in front of a problem that human brain manages easily, adding cabbages and potatoes (making soup for example) but computer does not. Here, conceptual modeling or abstract representation of your dataset (like the Harris matrix, Harris 1989) could help you. You need to think of the way you can translate some of your data in other shapes and formats and if this is necessary or not. If yes, you come back to the second kind, if not, you are nearly finished. This step is the interpretation step.

As a conclusion, all these steps could be seen as integration degrees. Do you need the higher degree to obtain useful things?

Looking in details, these steps are closely linked, without overlapping to the multi/trans/inter disciplinary schemes. This is not the path we follow here, but in the shape of the SAGA, taking into account the disciplines represented, and some discussion we have with archaeologist, part of the data integration is linked to the people integration. This is a bit of philosophical and it is where I am stopping for this part.

3- List of existing software or framework which can help to do data integration

In theory, you have two ways to do data integration. This is coming from the computer scientist dealing with data which are for them digital information. First way is to define your data scheme before your study. Then all the data acquired will be in the same framework and you will manage it in a dedicated interface. For example this is what has been done in Drap et al. 2017. Usually this way involves computer scientist and is the results of long thoughts prior to its build. This is equivalent to build a data warehouse.

The second and most common is gathering multi sources datasets and making them compatible by using wrapping/mediation tools. These tools are manual or automated process which make your data useful for an integrated viewing and processing. Recent examples could be found in Agapiou et al. 2018, Wadoux et al. 2018, Wang et al. 2019 and Xiong et al. 2019.

At this point, we only give some pieces of framework which can help to do integration, some software can handle a lot in a ready to use interface, other need to be customized and some programming skills could be useful. This list is not closed and every one could feel free to add more softwares. The idea is to propose freely distributed software.

Concerning the physical modelling and inversion, you could refer to the WG3 task 2.7.

Concerning the conceptual/ontology based modelling, no specific software has been found. It appears that you should define your ontology and then you have methods and programming languages to implement it. For further reading see WG3 Task 2.2

-R packages

R is a high level programming language based on S which is design for statistical analysis. A lot of statistical methods are present in R and a lot of packages come to enhance its potentialities in special methods

- -Geostatistics
Rgeostats (<http://rgeostats.free.fr/>)
gstat (<https://github.com/r-spatial/gstat/>)
- -Compositional analysis
Compositional (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/Compositional/index.html>)

-Python packages

Python is a programming language. It is widely use in science and data management especially the SciPy ecosystem. It provides you with a lot of mathematical and computational packages. It is meaningless to list them, but searching with keywords and python would provide you with information. It is interesting to use because the freedom permitted by programing allow to handle dataset in a unified framework. The main issue is to have some programing skills.

-GIS

QGIS is an open source GIS software in which extension can be written. Current version of the software is 3.12.1 (<https://www.qgis.org/>). Some plugin for archaeology and geophysics have been developed (but compatibility issues can appear if it were developed for QGIS 2)

-LIME (Buckley et al. 2019)

LIME is a software developed by the VOG team (<http://virtualoutcrop.com/>). It permits the 3D visualization of the data. The processing should be done before and outside of it.

-Useful additional links:

Information and documents on the CIDOC conceptual reference model could be found on the website <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>

-pyGIMLi Geophysical Inversion and Modeling Libray (<https://www.pygimli.org/>)

pyGIMLi is an open-source library for modelling and inversion and in geophysics. The object-oriented library provides management for structured and unstructured meshes in 2D and 3D, finite-element and finite-volume solvers, various geophysical forward operators, as well as Gauss-Newton based frameworks for constrained, joint and fully-coupled inversions with flexible regularization.

-ArchaeoFusion (<http://archaeofusion.com/>)

ArchaeoFusion is a tool for Archaeologists and others who use ground geophysical sensors to build subsurface maps. ArchaeoFusion will load data from many sources, processes the data, and then integrate it into a clear representation of subsurface features.

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